

TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES

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Annotation: The role and the effective usage of innovative technologies in teaching English are considered in this article. The Internet links, which are effectively used during the lessons, are also shown here.

Key words: Innovative technologies, multimedia, Internet links, electronic resources, learning environment, motivation.

The digital age has changed the conditions of life, formation and education. Everything changes around, and accordingly, the attitude towards learning must change. The content of education in a modern comprehensive school remains unilateral; state standards based on an objective approach are morally outdated. Many modern teachers point to the lack of a competent approach, focused on the individuality of the student. Education at school does not give students a clearly expressed positive motivation to choose a life path, interests and prospects. Now, in the 21st century, the role of international education is growing. To raise own culture, to develop and to go forward is a vital necessity of our century and the young state. The same vital necessity is the study of foreign languages in order to keep pace with the times. Today, knowledge of English opens a window into a large global world with its wide flow of information and innovations. At the present stage of the development of the society, the modernization of the content of education in Uzbekistan is not connected with the innovation processes in the organization of teaching foreign languages. Therefore, the main goal of the modern teacher is to increasingly. Since the main goal of teaching foreign languages is the formation and development of a communicative culture of schoolchildren, the training of practical mastering a foreign language, the use of computer technology, Internet resources is the best approach in teaching. It's been quite a few years since a computer entered our

life, and we no longer imagine a modern lesson without the use of information technology. ICT becomes an integral tool in increasing students' interest and developing visual-figurative thinking. Everyone understood that the use of ICT in the learning process has the potential to activate cognitive, intellectual and independent activities of students. Information technology makes it is possible to change significantly the forms and methods of academic work. In the education system ICT can be divided into two types: hardware (computer, printer, scanner, camera, video camera, audio and video tape recorder, etc.) and software (electronic textbooks, simulators, test environments, information sites, search systems Internet, etc.). Nowadays the computer is an effective assistant and integral part of everyone, which allows to improve the quality of training and the effectiveness of control. Currently, the use of computers in the educational process is very important. I want to focus on the use of computer presentations in the educational process. The use of presentations allows to every teacher to intensify mastering of educational material by students and conduct classes at a qualitatively new level, instead of using a regular blackboard projecting slide films from the computer screen to a large wall-mounted screen or a personal computer (laptop) for each student. Colorfully designed presentations (using animation effects, in the form of text, a diagram, a graphic, a drawing.) solve the problem of using visual material. For example, if you previously cut and paste pictures on the board, then now you can find pictures with the help of Internet and insert them on the slide right away. If there is a lot of pictures, then make a few slides. At the lessons of the introduction of new material, one can use the following educational programs: great help in teaching phonetics, articulation, rhythmic intonation pronunciation skills, to increase the motivation of students to learn English is provided by the program «Professor Higgins. English without an accent» The interactive course» choose the methods and forms of organizing the learning activity of trainees, which optimally meet the goal. In recent years, the usage of new information technologies in schools has been raised Round-up (publisher Pearson Education Limited, Longman), consisting of several disks of different levels, is a great help in studying and fixing grammar. Exercises are arranged according to

grammatical themes. Advantages of the course are the ability to check their answers and summarizing the results of the tasks with computers. Interactive course «Way Ahead» (Macmillan publishing house) — there are six levels of this course including games, crosswords, fascinating exercises for fixing grammatical and lexical material in a game form. Interesting and exciting is a sound and graphic design of the program. In the language laboratory there are disks with various type of educational programs. This is an important and extensive addition to the training process. The educational programs provide a large number of exercises for grammar and vocabulary. These programs are very easy to use, you need minimal computer skills, which is very important when working with a group of students. There are materials for all classes that are divided into modules, but their content is very simple and not very clear. Now let's move on to the issue of using the Internet for teaching English. Today, new methods of using Internet resources are opposed to traditional teaching foreign languages. To teach communication in a foreign language, you need to create real life situations that will stimulate the study of the material and develop adequate behavior.

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